

Media and Democratic Governance in Nigeria: An Analysis of Governor Danbaba Suntuai's Image Makers News Management Strategies

By

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Abstract

Image makers and political propagandists tend to use the media to maximize favorable publicity as well as alter the spread of negative news against their clients. Using content analysis of purposely selected three of the major national newspapers in Nigeria; *Daily Trust*, *The Punch* and *The Nigerian Tribune*, the paper explores the practical news management strategies used by the image makers of Taraba State Governor, Danbaba Suntuai, to control and/or manipulate news of their client. The Governor suffers from “brain damage” after an air crash when he was piloting his jet which crash landed on 25th October, 2012. The main objective of this study is to highlight the strategies the image makers of the “incapacitated” Governor had been using variety of techniques, for about three years, through the media for the attainment of their political objectives of keeping the governor in the helm of affairs of State. The stance of the spin doctors is seen as a violation of the rule of law where the Governor could have been constitutionally impeached. The study buttresses the facts that image makers could be detrimental to the entrenchment of constitutional democracy, inimical to unhindered freedom of information and unhealthy to ethical journalism practices. The work, therefore, recommends ways of dealing with political public relations managers and journalists relations.

Keywords: Political Public Relations, News Management, Strategies, Nigeria

1.1 Introduction

Mass media is an important avenue of political communication. The Nigerian political history is embedded with stories of travails and struggles by the media from the colonial Nigeria to the commitment for attainment of the nation's independent. The Nigerian media strove to survive under draconian and obnoxious military rules. The efforts of the media in re-enthronement of a civilian democratic Nigeria have been well documented.

However, the coterie of men and women in the corridor of power tend to deter journalists' quest for discharging their constitutionally recognized responsibilities. The media has been a subject of manipulation and bogus propaganda by some elements who

want to use the media in their favor. The political public relations in the Nigerian media prove to be a “hide-and-seek” game of denial and distortion of verifiable facts. This has caused difficulties to journalists in the quest to ethically provide true, objective and accurate reports of events as they unfold.

The paper adopts qualitative content analysis using a sample of three of the major national dailies in Nigeria – *The Punch*, *Daily Trust* and *The Nigerian Tribune*. Purposively selected cases of political public relations have been studied. The work traces the historical background of the relationship between the press and politics in the Nigerian media communication environment. It has re-established the link and bond between politics and media relations.

The operations of some political public relations specialists from the office of the Taraba State Governor have shown how the discovery of facts and truthful and accurate information can be endangered. The use of the media to distort the truth as well as to prevent the public from having access to unbiased and objective information has proved to be detrimental to the entrenchment of an ideal democratic society.

The paper seeks to address what Lilleker and Temple (2013) referred to as a “key challenge for political journalists” which is about “how to avoid becoming a megaphone for party and government propaganda machines – and avoid acting merely as a conduit for the ideological preferences of their employers – while still providing up to date commentary on key political events of the day in a way that engages and serves their wider audience” (p. 283).

Spin doctors are generally defined as public relations consultants or spokespersons employed to maintain or improve as well as influence public opinion. The concept of “spin doctoring” as a technique is an integrated political marketing and campaigning strategy for attaining favorable image and acceptability. It seeks to manage interaction with the public through mass media to ensure acceptance of policies, agenda and re-election bid.

Shu’aibu (2008) opines that “spin doctor is a slang which describes a person who publicizes favourable interpretations of the words and actions of a public figure,

especially a politician. Public relations persons object to being described as such, because they believe the phrase has derogatory connotation and is more appropriate for those who specialize in turning black to white and vice versa.

However, according to Stockwell (2000), spin doctors have variety of names - media advisers, communication managers and press secretaries, but mostly are employed to take care of political well-being of their clients in the media. Other staffers are equally employed and drawn into the work of spins. They may include speech-writers, policy advisers/administrators.

Spin doctors may not necessarily be called as such. Personalities that may be described as “spin doctors” may work in “public relations” or count themselves as “spokespersons”, but their job is intrinsically the same –“to make sure that the coverage their organization or clients receive is the coverage they want” (Street, 2011:188).

1.2 Objectives of the Paper

The main aim of the paper is to examine the relationship between political public relations and news management in the Nigerian Democracy. The objectives of the paper are thus:

- i.** To highlights the strategies the aides used in their attempt to cover/hide the facts of truth from the journalists and the general public.
- ii.** Elucidate the democratic implications, and historical conundrums such image makers could cause through the media.
- iii.** Enumerate ways in which political journalists could relate with spin doctors in a bid to keep the public properly informed.

2.1 Manifestation of Image Makers in Media Management

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According to Gwandu (2014), in Nigerian political context, spin doctors could have any of the following or similar titles: Minister of Information; Commissioner of Information; Director of Information; Media Adviser; Special Adviser on Media and Publicity; Political Adviser; Special Adviser on Public Affairs; Special Assistant on Political Matters; Communication Manager; Publicity Secretary; Information Officer; Media Liaison Officer; Press Secretary; Political Consultant; Media Manager; Public Relations Officer/ Manager; and Corporate Communication Officer.

Street (2011) elaborates the role of spin doctors in influencing political communication. As he cites Gaber (2000), Street says that “spin doctoring” refers to a number of activities and individuals. Street (2011) asserts that the role of spin doctors included “gate keeping” of journalistic access, granting or denying interviews, as well as briefing interviewees on what to say and what not to say.

“It also includes glossing of stories or speeches to journalists, pushing particular lines or interpretations.... It means creating good photo-opportunities, or making sure that journalists and photographers are in the right place at the right time. It involves the writing of the speeches, and of the accompanying press releases, and it extends to pressuring or persuading journalists through threats and flattery, to represent your employer or client favourably” (Street, 2011:188)

It has been established that spin doctors use the media to achieve one or some of the following goals: (i) informing the publics of "favorable" publicity; (ii) clarification of certain issues; (iii) convincing the masses on the rationale behind "unpopular" policies"; (iv) restoration of the image of the client; (v) projection of the image of their officers; (vi)

showing responsiveness of the officers concerned; (vii) countering rumors, propaganda and public "misinformation"; and (viii) stopping negative publicity from spreading.

All the activities of spin doctors of both “below-the-line” and “above-the-line” including kite-flying, firebreak, stoking the fire, milking a story, laundering (Gaber, 2000b, Franklin, 2005) are geared toward “media management”. In this context, McNair (2011:123) defines media management as “the wide variety of practices whereby political actors may seek to control, manipulate or influence media organizations in ways which correspond to their political objectives”. These activities may include pseudo-events, image management, political marketing, pro-active and re-active information management among others.

Shu’aibu (2008) notes that “the professional spin doctors use the media anonymously to divulge sensitive information or reckless insinuations, to cast aspersion on presumed opponents while portraying their principals in favorable spotlight in the battle of wits”.

He asserts that spin doctoring can be done by a number of people including nonprofessional. Using the appointment and redeployment of the then Chairman of the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC), Malam Nuhu Ribadu, Shu’aibu (2008) highlights how the process of “spinning” has been carried out by almost all the people within the various strata of society.

Almost all major opinion molders including the media, clerics, scholars, lawyers, activists amongst others have engaged in spinning to either eulogize or castigate the parties in the brouhaha over the man's redeployment for capacity building at the prestigious National Institute of Policy and Strategic Studies (NIPSS) in Jos Plateau State. Everyone seems to be an unsolicited spin doctor for the parties involved”, he says.

2.2 Concerns about Spin Doctors’ Roles in Politics of Media Management

At a time when face-to-face political communication is becoming almost impossible to all the social groups constituting the society, the most common contact point between politicians and masses is through the mass media. The mass media offers a forum for information delivery in a “comprehensible and accessible” manner (Franklin, 2004). The media (re)present and project politicians to the masses. It is on the basis of the information available to the masses that they make informed choices or form opinions.

The public tends to believe the media as the fourth estate of the realm and are seen as the watchdog on behalf of the public. The media's role is to keep the public properly informed while at the same time holding the government accountable (Section 22 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria).

Prasad (2003) notes: 'The mass media are important in shaping the political process; they are the channels for the diffusion of constructive ideas, promoting enlightenment, public opinion, highlighting process of governance, serve as a forum for political debate and are watchful of the excess and violations of the development rights of citizens'.

Considering the role of the media as a pillar of democracy and being acknowledged as an avenue that audience turns to for information, many spin doctors and propagandists find the media as a vital tool for favourable publicity at the same time trying to alter negative news against their clients from spreading. In doing so, the media's credibility is put to question (Davies 2008; Louw 2005; Lewis et al 2005).

The recent democratic dispensation gave oxygen for the Nigerian media industry to thrive, yet the channels of political communication are said to be degraded by manipulation. The Media are falling prey to partisanship, anti-democratic politics of propaganda, deception and distortion of facts (Hargreaves & Thomas, 2002). Critics argue that corrosive influence of spin result into unethical media practices in the political discourse. Pundits put the blame on spin doctors who mould the information and communication in political arena for the consumption of the media and digestion of the citizens.

Spin doctors write the script, politicians perform the script as actors, the media provide the stage, and the journalists report the drama for the entertainment of us, the audience. Apart from the fact that Public Relations works more on behalf of the powerful in the society, spin doctoring distracts attention from the substance of politics (Oso: 2012, pg 57).

According to Oates (2008), journalists have become progressively more educated as well as increasingly the target of public relations tactics. She says there appears to be a sort of symbiotic relationship between journalists and politicians. It is on this note that Lilleker and Temple (2013) assert:

It is important that the public have access to relatively impartial political information, and not partly political propaganda and 'spin', passed on by lazy or partisan political journalists. The misleading information about Iraq's non-existent 'weapon of mass destruction', used to justify the invasion of Iraq in 2003, was peddled to the public by journalists who failed to interrogate New Labour's spin machine. Such failures have damaged the reputation of political journalism in Britain, as have claims about the over simplification and personalization of political coverage (pg 285).

According to Davis (2002) journalists have become the targets of public relations tactics. Oates (2008) maintains that there appears to be a sort of symbiotic relationship between journalists and politicians. Weaver and Wilhoit (1996) and MacDonald (2006) observe that lack of sense of professional standard; proper journalism training and ethical inculcation account for journalists' relying on spin doctors for their reports. With job insecurity, fear of intimidation and physical violence against reporters, salary reduction and increase pay of corporate communication and public relations practitioners and increasing market competition "journalists find it difficult to resist relying on the sources of well-funded PR campaigns instead of careful independent reporting" (Oates, 2008).

Political analysts and media critics have been showing great concern, especially in mature democracies around the world that channels of political communication have been distorted by manipulation and anti-democratic effects of "manufacturers of consent" (Herman and Chomsky, 1988) with spin doctors at the receiving end. Stockwell (2005) notes:

The argument goes that the application of spin to political communication is a negative force grinding force down the substance of our language and our democracy. Critics argue that the corrosive influence of spin is evident in the rise of misleading political advertising, negative campaigning and new forms of propaganda. Politicians, with the assistance of their media advisers, do seek to subtly orchestrate the symbolic spectacle of the politics, set the terms of political debate and rapidly adjust their policies to any changes in public sentiment... whenever the spin doctor plays fast and loose with the truth and comes between the politician and the public, there is some validity in the view that they are a negative influence on the quality of democracy.

According to Pate & Maikaba (2014) "this is why citizens feel threatened when the supposed watchdog is weak and appear unable to act appropriately; behave in contrast to

societal and professional expectations or get mortgaged to sectional, commercial and manipulative predispositions”.

2.3 The Emergence of Viable Spin Doctors in Contemporary Nigeria

The Nigerian political atmosphere has witnessed an unprecedented change from 1999 onwards. The year is a turning point in the democratic Nigeria. The then Military Head of State, General Abubakar Abdussalam, successfully handed over to the fourth republic civilian administration. A retired General Olusegun Obasanjo was declared winner of the 1999 Nigeria’s presidential election for a four year term. He was later re-elected to complete the constitutionally provided possible two terms of four years each.

After the completion of his second tenure and the aborted third term ambition, General Obasanjo single-handedly chose the then sick and ailing governor of Katsina State – Umar Musa Yar’adua. The choice was said to be informed by the relationship Obasanjo enjoyed with the elder brother of the former, General Musa Yar’adua. The then presidential candidate, Umar Musa Yar’adua, was rumored dead even during the 2011 political campaign. Adeniyi (2011) quoted Obasanjo saying:

Soon after he was returned as the elected president and assumed duty, President Umar Musa ‘Yar’adua’s health condition aggravated. He was a frequent visitor at German hospital and later transferred his medication to a Saudi Arabian hospital.

When President Yar’adua was to leave for Saudi Arabia for medication he intended to write and communicate to the National Assembly that he was going for vacation. His special adviser on media and publicity, Olusegun Adeniyi writes “I left the president, feeling very relieved and thinking that I could spin the positives out of the leave if he could notify the National Assembly of his intention to go on vacation as he promised to do” (Pg176). He dismissed the question from the media whether the president leave was connected to his illness. “I explained that every president needs trip away from the pressure of office to relax, rejuvenate and possibly reflect and unwind” (p178-179).

Yar’adua’s last medical trip to Saudi Arabia was shrouded with a lot of political imbroglio. He left on November 24, 2009 and brought back at night on February 24, 2010. He was kept in the presidential villa as a president till 5th May 2010 when he eventually died. Throughout the period, he was kept away from the public glare. Even the Vice President and top government functionaries were denied access to him.

During the absence of the President in Nigeria, many media houses reported that he travelled to an undisclosed hospital for an undisclosed ailment. The lacuna resulted in the belief that the president might have died or became incapacitated. There were calls from various strata of Nigerian stakeholders that the President should be declared impeached pursuant to Sections 144-148 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. A few of the President's supporters described any attempt to impeach the president as callous and unnecessary (Adeniyi, 2011).

The spin doctors including members of the family of the president especially his wife, Hajiya Turai 'Yar'adua, kept the president incommunicado. The Special Adviser to the President, Segun Adeniyi talks about the media and reportage on some issue regarding the incidents. "My interview was lavishly aired on all the television channels and print media the next day, and I felt that the subtle rebuttal would at least attract some sympathy and would help defuse the tension" (P247).

While I had hopes that he will recover, I had no illusions that the person I had seen that day would ever be strong enough to resume as president within the time left for his mandate to elapse. That explains why I was quite skeptical when stories suggesting he had fully recovered began to surface. There were tales in the media about the president being sighted walking in the garden or going to the library. I knew they were lies and told to every editor or reporter that contacted me to ignore such tales. Some did, but some still went ahead to publish lies as they were fed" (Adeniyi, 2011:250-251).

On the basis of this and related episodes, political communication circuit in Nigerian media can be diagrammatically represented as follows:

Diagram 1: Linear model of spin doctoring in Nigerian media

Key: M = Message

M+ = Message with additional information

N = New/Different Message

The linear model shows that Spin Doctors pass a message (M) to the Mass Media. The Mass Media may offer a “preferred” relay of the message by giving out the message as passed by the spin doctors. Other media houses could offer a “negotiated” relay of the message and some media houses could offer an “oppositional” or altered the message from the spin doctors. The general public who are exposed to this variety of the media messages will swimming in a pool of information about the same issue.

Diagram 2 Multi-dimensional model of spin doctoring in Nigerian media.

Key: M = Message

M+ = Message with additional information

N = New/Different Message

This diagram is an extension of the linear model where the message from the spin doctors passes through the media that give at least three different accounts of the same issue. Here the message could reach to opinion leaders who will present it to the general public. In this diagram there is an element of feedback either directly from general public to the media or through the opinion leaders who can equally initiate their own feedback to the media. The Spin doctors are normally consulted by the Media. The diagram also shows possibility of disseminating the message by the general publics who get their message to other individuals.

3.0 Methodology

The paper adopts case study method of qualitative content analysis. Kothari (2012) says that the case study method focuses on full and in-depth analysis on issues. “The object of the case study method is to locate the factors that account for behavior-patterns of the given unit as an integrated totality”. In the words of Odum (1929) as cited in Koul (2012)

“the case study method is a technique by which individual factors whether it be an institution or just an episode in the life of an individual or a group is analyzed in relationship to any other in the group”. It involves careful and a fairly exhaustive observation of a unit – person, family, institution, cultural group, community or issues, for the purpose of drawing inferences and possible generalization (Young, 1960). Yin (2003) views the case study method as an empirical inquiry that uses multiple of sources of evidence to investigate a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, in which the boundaries between the phenomenon and its context are not clearly evident. According to Wimmer and Dominick (2011) the case study method is the “most valuable when the researcher wants to obtain a wealth of information about a research topic. The case study and provides tremendous details”. The paper use inductive method of data analysis. Citing Merriam (1988), Wimmer and Dominick says “most case studies depend on inductive reasoning. Principles and generalization emerge from an examination of the data. Many case studies attempt to discover new relationships rather than verify existing hypothesis”.

4.1 Governor Danbaba Suntai’s Image Makers’ News Management Strategies

Late President Umar Musa Yar’adua’s saga seems to have provided a template for spin doctors’ political communication in Nigeria. Suntai’s case could be described as a replay of the tactics earlier adopted to retain the seat of presidency for the Yar’aduas during his sickness.

The Taraba State Governor, Danbaba Suntai was piloting his jet Cessna 208, 5N-BMJ when it crashed on October 25th, 2012. The Governor, aide-de-camp and Chief Security Officer were in Germany barely 48 hours later (Punch, 2012).

Various strategies and techniques were adopted by the spin doctors to achieve their goals which posed ethical challenges to journalists’ efforts of discovering the truth about illness or otherwise of the Governor.

However, the Secretary to the Taraba State Government, Timothy Kataps, in an interview published by *The Punch* of September 8, 2013 “Sunta’s return guided by Constitution – Taraba SSG” debunked the linkage between Yar’adua and Suntai case.

1. Silence as a Strategy:

The first strategy adopted by the image makers was to ensure total blackout of the issue in the media. The spin doctors try to achieve this by avoiding the press, keeping mum and avoiding any comment on the matter. The Nigerian Tribune finds it imperative to highlight this strategy in an editorial “Suntai: The Conspiracy of Silence” published on August 2nd 2013.

2. Claiming that the Governor was Hale and Hearty:

After spending first three months for medication, there were calls for the impeachment of Danbaba Suntai. Former Senator Saleh Danboyi was among those demanding for governor’s removal on health ground. The Taraba State PDP debunked the call claiming that the governor was in a good condition of health and will be returning to Nigeria soon. This was said to have been done in order to save the governor’s political career. The Punch of January, 12, 2013 reported that the state PDP Chairman, Victor Kona, claims that the governor is “well and will be back in the country”. Adding that:

I spoke with him 40 minutes ago and spent the entire holiday season in Hannover, Germany and just came back last weekend. I can authoritatively announce to you that Governor Suntai is in a stable condition and will soon be in Nigeria to continue the good works he is doing in Taraba State. He is currently in a private apartment undergoing physiotherapy and receiving visitors. Contrary to speculations, the governor did not sustain any brain or spinal cord injuries and he is not partially paralysed. He is in a right frame of mind and speaks, eats and drinks.

However, the journalists wanted to be sure of what they were told. They requested the state Party Chairman to speak with Suntai on phone in their presence for them to verify the truth which he refused. “We cannot call the governor because it would constitute a security breach. The Speaker of the state House of Assembly, Secretary to the State Government and Chief Judge of Taraba State travelled to Germany and as I speak with you now, they are with Governor Suntai in Germany, he said.” (Punch, 12, January, 2013).

It took eight months before the party issued another release announcing the arrival the Governor who spent about 10 months before his first return to Nigeria on August 25, 2013.

3. Providing “Arranged” Pictures and Photographs:

The Governor’s image makers also use the strategy of clicking arranged pictures of the ailing governor in order to show to the media that will inform the public that the

Governor was in a good condition of health. Some of the pictures were criticized to offer meanings which were never intended.

4. Barring Media from their Client:

Journalists were shielded from conducting their professional duty by the crony of Danbaba Suntai's spin doctors. For instance, the journalists were barred from talking to the Governor and he was neither allowed to speak to the press. The *Nigerian Tribune* on Sunday 25th August, 2012 published its story with a title "Wife, associates bar media coverage of Suntai's arrival". On August, 26th, 2013 *The Punch* titled "Suntai arrives Abuja, assisted out of aircraft". The paper reported that "he was shielded from responding to questions from journalists by heavily armed security personnel".

The paper quoted a friend to Suntai, John Dara, said, "I am fully in the picture in all the arrangements for his return and we are really excited to see him back. What is clear is that after the long haul flight from the US, he is obviously weak and tired...Normally, talking to press can be spontaneous and can be organised; but we felt that when he has rested well, it will be easier for him to address the press logically."

5. Use of Recorded Video Broadcast

In what can be described as snob appeal propaganda technique, the spin doctors also adopted the use of recorded video to claim state-wide broadcast.

6. Circulation of Controversial Letter:

The Governor arrived Nigeria after 10 month of medical trip. Media said that he looked frail and was aided to alight out of the aircraft and did not speak to anyone at the airport. "From NAIA to Jalingo Airport, he did not utter a word to the crowd that had gathered to welcome him." (Punch August 27, 2013). Yet, the following morning a letter was said to have been submitted to the State House of Assembly claiming that he was alright indicating to resume duty immediately. (Punch 27, August, 2013).

7. Use of Testimonies:

It was during the same period that Adamawa State Governor, Murtala Nyako, visited Danbaba Suntai and shed tears on the condition he met the latter. While addressing newsmen Nyako said "you saw me shedding tears of joy. I am very happy. I can now go back to my state (Adamawa) and tell my people" (Punch 27, August, 2013). The use of

Professor of Geography, Gery Gana from Niger state to testify that the governor was fit to go back to the office is another example of testimonies.

8. Preventing The Formulation of Medical Panel:

The call for upholding to the constitution in probing the health condition of the Governor was seen as an attempt to get impeached him. The image makers were not happy with the mood. Daily Trust of 1 January, 2014 in a story titled “Ex-aides allege move to declare Suntai incapacitated” quoted a former aide of the Governor who craved for anonymity saying that: “If the plans go well, Suntai may be declared incapacitated by a panel of medical experts to be constituted by the state executive. After the assessment and declaration, the ailing governor would be impeached”.

9. Circulation of Recorded Video:

Another strategy adopted by the spin doctors to curb journalists from the discovery of the truthful information was a video footage given to news men. The table turns when the video that was supposed to prove the governor was heal and hearty turns show the governor confirming that he is not fit to return to the office.

Daily Trust of 28th January, 2014 published a story with a title “Video shows Suntai admitting inability to return to office”. The paper quoted the governor making disjointed and rambling over issues when asked about his message to Nigeria and ability to return to office. The footage was said have been shown to journalists by Civil Society Network Against Corruption in Lagos.

On January 29, 2014 Daily Trust published a story titled “Suntai video has vindicated us -Legislator”. In the story one of the 15 lawmakers who issued a statement arguing the Governor to return abroad for medication was quoted to have described the video as a vindication of their earlier stance.

On January 29th, 2014 Daily Trust attempted to unearth the source of the video and how it get to the public. A story “... How the Video Emerge”. After presenting the video which turns to prove contrary than the expected, the spin doctors adopted another strategy. This time is the strategy of denial and accusation. The Punch on January 30, 2014 published a story that suntai’s aides described the video as fake.

10. Name Calling: Diving the People into Pro-Suntai and Anti-Suntai Camps

The spin doctors adopted the strategy when describing the Acting governor as being disloyal to the ailing governor and that those who are calling for the removal of the governor as people who want to cause chaos in the state. “These people are not fair to his Excellency, and they are wicked. Taraba people are not with them, and even the Majority Leader of the House has disassociated himself from them. What they are doing is unconstitutional and a violation of Nigerian laws,” he said.

5.1 Conclusion

From the above, an attempt has been made to analyze the strategies used by Governor Danbaba Suntai’s spin doctors in the contemporary political communication of democratic Nigeria. The study finds at least the following strategies:

1. Shielding clients from journalists who would like to access them.
2. Speaking and presentation of information to the media on behalf of their clients.
3. Offering excuses when journalists attempt to contact or verify spin doctors claims.
4. Keeping mum on issues and trying to avoid media discovery on the issues.
5. Diverting attention through arranged pictures, videos and “forged” letters.
6. Keeping journalists waiting for speculative press conferences.
7. Re-acting and countering any negative publicity on their clients.

The papers finds out that the activities of the spin doctors could serve as an impediment to journalists in the discovery and dissemination of truth or not. It is found that activities are inimical to a democratic setting that canvasses for freedom of expression and freedom of press.

Moreover, such issues are coming at a time Nigeria – the emerging democracy in Africa, has passed into law Freedom of Information Bill into law. The bill seeks to empower journalists and any information seeker to get information demanded. The denial of which is considered as a violation of the act.

Nigerian journalists, face daunting challenges in a bid to find out and verify information which spin doctors find inimical to their clients. The relationship between journalists and spin doctors may not always be symbiotic unless when the former find it favorable to the continued operation of their master.

Journalists and mass media struggle under tremendous pressure to serve the general public and nurture the democratic system. The activities of some spin doctors if not checked may not auger well for a smooth and healthy information dissemination system in a democratic society. The study recommends: further investigation into the relationship between Political Public Relations Officers (PPRO) and journalists, organizing workshops and symposia to both journalists and PPRO, formulation of appropriate legislations to deal with those who deny journalists information and enhancement of media relations with PPRO through symbiotic collaboration.

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